

ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK PROVERBS ABOUT LABOUR

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Annotation: this thesis is the main content of English and Uzbek paremiology devoted to the analysis of one of the large groups of proverbs. To diligence and laziness related proverbs are taken as an example of two languages, and various semantic features are mutually analyzed.

Key words: paremiology, educational value, characteristic, advice, diligence, laziness, reproach, qawlun

Proverbs (proverbs) are an important part of Uzbek folklore and by analyzing them, studying their content, methods of expression and functions, it helps us to understand our cultural values. Proverbs have been included in our speech since ancient times, but few people think about their origin. Because there were no stable phraseological units in those times. Nevertheless, proverbs helped to form a new communication culture. The proverbs mentioned in our ancient epics are still used today in the speech and literature of our people without losing their significance, in short, to express thoughts in a short, concise way. The term "proverb" is derived from the Arabic word "qawlun" - to speak, to say. The history of the study of the proverb genre goes back to Mahmud Koshgari. About 400 proverbs and sayings were included in his work "Devonu Lug'atit Turk", besides which we can see that special attention was paid to proverbs in the works of Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur and others. We also come across many stories where proverbs are used instead of the beginning of words. "The death of a horse is the death of a dog" as an epigraph in the story "Thief" holiday" proverb is quoted. In addition to the skill of this writer, it seems to reveal the essence of the story in one proverb.

Analysis of the semantic, linguo-pragmatic and linguo-spiritual typology of proverbs on the topic "work" helps to identify similarities and differences in two languages (English and Uzbek). Let's take a look at each typology.

Uzbek folk proverbs have long reflected the life experiences of our people, high respect for work and perseverance. Valuing work and striving for it is one of the main qualities of the Uzbek people. Below we present the most famous and meaningful proverbs of the Uzbek people about work. These proverbs

appreciate not only the value of work, but also human values such as patience, justice and honesty.

Semantic typology is the analysis of the meaning of proverbs, indicators and concepts in them. Proverbs on the topic of "work" usually include statements about the importance of work, useful and necessary aspects of work, positive and negative effects of work results.

Uzbek proverbs: " Davlat qochar, mehnat quvar" - permanent, positive result of labor. " Davlat ham egiz-egiz, Mehnat ham egiz-egiz " - success cannot be achieved without work. "Yetmish go'zallikning bittasi — mehnat". "Tekinning minnati ko'p, Mehnatning — ziynati". English proverbs: "No pain, no gain" - there is no result without hard work. "Hard work pays off" - work has a result.

Lingvopragmatic typology is the use of proverbs in society, their purpose and effect. Proverbs are often used in different situations depending on the social and cultural context. In Uzbek context: Proverbs are used in family upbringing, explaining the value of work. Promotes desire for work, appreciation of work and respect for workers in society. In English context: Proverbs are used to encourage business and social success, to encourage people to work. "Work hard, dream big" - this proverb is used to encourage the aspirations of young people in business.

Linguistic typology is the spiritual, moral and pedagogical significance of proverbs. This typology studies the philosophy of work, its place and value in human life. In Uzbek culture:

Work is one of the main values of humanity, to work, to strive for a fair life. "Labor is the correction of broken things" - the spiritual significance of labor. In English culture: Work is important in the personal development and social status of a person. "Diligence is the mother of good luck" - hard work and aspiration bring good luck. Because proverbs have a wide range of meanings, they are used in every sphere of society possible In this regard, English and Uzbek folk proverbs are similar both in terms of meaning and application is very close. In the course of studying proverbs in English and Uzbek languages in terms of volume we witnessed more encounters of proverbs about work. The reason for this is different we can bring. For example, earning a reputation by working hard, being able to cover your needs issues are proven not only in ancient times, but also today. Any achievement is based on hard work, perseverance and strong desire. Hard working and hardworking person

English and Uzbek people take such issues seriously as Uzbek and English proverbs finds the opposite. It is in the process of analyzing proverbs on this

topic that it is always positive to work highlighting issues such as being valued, and laziness and apathy being strongly condemned we observe In this work, the characteristics of some Uzbek and English proverbs about work we try to compare and analyze. Below are the Uzbek versions of some English proverbs on this topic.

Let's look at the meanings and alternatives in the language. 1) The laborer is worthy, of his hire. (Ishlab topganning — osh, Ishlamay topganing — tosh). 2) Work shall not eat, He that will not. (Ishlamagan — tishlamas, Ishyoqmasga kun kulmas). 3) He that is afraid of wounds must not come near a battle. (Chumchuqdan qo'rqqan tariq ekmas, Chigirtkadan qo'rqqan — ekin) 4) The early bird catches the worm. (Muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun erta turish kerak) 5) Actions speak louder than words. (Harakatlar so'zlardan ko'ra balandroq gapiradi.) 6) Easy come, easy go. (Oson kelgan narsa oson ketadi) 7) A man of words and not of deeds is like a garden full of weeds. (Ishlamasdan so'zlovchi odam o't bosgan bog'ga o'xshar.). 8) Head cook and bottle washer. (Ham bosh oshpaz, ham tovoq yuvuvchi. Bir yigitga yetmish ikki hunar oz) 9) Handsome is that handsome does. (Ishi go'zal odam, o'zi ham go'zaldir. Ishing bo'lsa sharofat, Hech ko'rmaysan kasofat). 10) Never put off till tomorrow what may be done today. (Bugun qila oladigan ishni hech qachon ertaga qoldirma. Bugungi ishni ertaga qo'yma) 11) Speak less but do more. (Ko'p gapirma, ko'p ishla. Kam gapirib ko'p ishla) 12) The workman is known by his work. (Usta ishi bilan mashhur. Usta, ishni qilar yuzta).

As you can see, proverbs about work are available in both Uzbek and English languages it shows that the people are very hardworking and hardworking. Therefore, all the proverbs we have noted. It is one of the topics that are widely used in people's lifestyle. Here they are even if we talk about the scope of meaning, it is the same thing, that is, the way of using proverbs is exactly the same we can understand that. For example: —"A man of words and not of deeds is like a garden full of weeds" when translating the proverb into Uzbek, it means "A person who talks without work is like a garden on fire" gives Through this proverb, we describe people who do not like work very much, but are lazy, but very talkative. But we the translation or meaning of an English proverb in Uzbek, always ready for the Uzbek language we can't use. As a very beautiful and alternative version of this, —If you know how to do it, you can do it, if you don't know how to do it we can quote "buzarsan". In Uzbek, as an equivalent to this proverb, —Work makes you hungry, you are lazy we can also use the proverb "he runs away from work." As another proof of our point,

English –Head if we consider the proverb cook and bottlewasher. Translation of the proverb in Uzbek –Ham the chief cook, also a dishwasher||. The meaning of the proverb is that one person is engaged in several jobs, or one is the owner of several professions at the same time. At first glance, the proverb has an educational value and to work shows exclamatory aspects. But the Uzbek translation always preserves the original of the proverb may not stay. And we always do it both in oral speech and in written speech, being ready for the language we can't use. The meaning of a proverb is always the words that make it up may not come from its meaning, but is related to its imagery. The time it is in use and depending on the situation it can be used in a new sense. That is, the emphasis on nim when the proverb is used is considered very important. The proverb can be used both positively and negatively. In this place the strength of figurativeness in proverbs leads to the same interpretation of the same proverb in both languages.

Summary

Proverbs around the topic of "work" in the two languages cover similar themes, but the context, philosophy and views of their social functions differ. This analysis helps to understand the attitudes of both cultures towards work. As proverbs express the conclusion of many centuries of life experiences, constant daily observations in the form of a complete thought in a strict polarity, they are dominated by the diversity of meaning of each word, the stability of phrases, and the stability of form. But depending on the place of use, their range of meaning is constantly expanding. That is why it is necessary to pay special attention to each word in the proverb. They have words that historically had completely different meanings.

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